

Newtonian Mechanics as the Driver of Special Relativity?

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Newtonian mechanics is often seen as a limiting case ($v \ll c$) of special relativity, but we ask: Why should the speed of light in a vacuum c appear as a limiting speed? We suggest that this question should already exist in Newtonian mechanics which assigns kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ and momentum $m_0 v$ to a particle with rest mass, m_0 . In Newtonian mechanics, it is already known that a rest mass represents inertia, i.e. a resistance to force. If a force moves the m_0 object creating kinetic energy, the inertia does not disappear ($m_0 dv/dt$) and so it is not far-fetched, we argue to suggest that instead of m_0 , one has $m(v)$ as an impedance which becomes m_0 for $v=0$. $m(v)$ is not m_0 constant + $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ because $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$ is obtained assuming $d/dt p = m_0 dv/dt$ and this would not hold for $m(v)$. The point we make is that as energy is added to a particle, its "new inertia" $m(v)$ becomes larger and larger making it more difficult to accelerate and leading to the idea of an upper bound speed. We argue that $\frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2 = \frac{1}{2} p v$ which is proportional to a Newtonian flux and if p is like impulse, it seems p flux should also be like an impedance. For example, m_0 is inertia (impedance) and so is $p=m_0 v$.

The question becomes: How does one solve for motion in such a case? We suggest that one may consider a transformation of $(p=0, m_0 \text{ constant})$ as seen in a rest frame to what is seen in a frame moving with $-v$. Such a frame sees the particle move with v which means that according to that frame a force must have been applied to the particle. The idea of Newtonian mechanics must be present, so, $m_0, p=0$ in the rest frame must be linked to a $m(v)$ and p in the moving frame and an upper bound speed should be present in the formulas. The energy and momentum should diverge to infinite as $v \rightarrow c$ (the upper bound speed) meaning that there is impedance stopping a particle with rest mass from attaining this upper speed. Furthermore, in the limit $v \ll c$, $p \rightarrow m_0 v$ and $E \rightarrow m_0 \text{ constant} + \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$. The transformation must be of the form:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v/c) & v/c & g(v/c) \\ v g(v/c) & g(v/c) & \end{vmatrix}$$

and $g(v/c)$ cannot be 1 as it must yield the v^2 term of $KE = \frac{1}{2}m_0 v^2$. Thus, even in the Newtonian limit, $g(v/c)$ is essential, one cannot have $(0, m_0 \text{ constant}) \rightarrow (m_0 v, m_0 \text{ constant})$. Even given the matrix above, one cannot solve for $g(v/c)$ without a further key consideration, we argue. This consideration is perhaps surprising given that a particle at rest with m_0 is considered to be completely different from one which has been accelerated to v . There would be no equivalence of the two. By using two frames, an m_0 is at rest in one while the second frame is considered to move with $-v$, while a person in the moving frame thinks he/she is at rest and that the particle moves. The scenarios are complementary (but have different directions) and the states $(0, m_0 \text{ constant})$ and $(p c, m(v) \text{ constant})$ must be linked, we argue. This is done through magnitudes (with a 1,-1 metric) which allows one to find $g(v/c)$ explicitly.

Now, c as an upper bound speed must be associated with 0 rest mass and seems to be linked to wave motion because $EE = ppcc + momo cccc \rightarrow E=pc$. There is no medium, so the wave is

a self-wave, and seems to be linked with a photon speed, but actually c is considered to be the speed of any object with no rest mass (e.g. gluon and neutrino before it was considered to have a tiny rest mass). Thus, c does not necessarily mean a direct link to electromagnetic theory, it seems, (even though this theory is directly linked to special relativity).

Newtonian Mechanics and an Upper Bound on Speed

Newtonian mechanics does not impose an upper bound on speed because one can always accelerate a particle with rest mass giving it more $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and momentum, $p = m_0 v$. We note that $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ follows from:

$$dp/dt = F \rightarrow m_0 dv = F dx dt/dx \rightarrow \text{Integral } m_0 v dv = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 = \text{Integral } F dx \quad ((1))$$

In other words, Newtonian mechanics uses m_0 and not $m(v)$ in p and so obtains $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$.

The main point we wish to make is that in Newtonian mechanics one has the notion of inertia associated with m_0 . m_0 is an impedance to force. If the force overcomes m_0 and gives it kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$, we suggest that it is not far-fetched to argue that this extra energy adds to the impedance of m_0 . If this were not the case, then this energy would simply exist associated with the particle, but not affecting the way in which it is accelerated, while rest mass affects the way it is accelerated. Why should $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ be impedance? We argue that $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 = \frac{1}{2} p v$ which is proportional to a Newtonian flux and if p is like impulse, it seems p flux should also be like an impedance. For example, m_0 is inertia (impedance) and so is $p = m_0 v$.

If one reasons along these lines, then it becomes harder and harder to accelerate a particle, leading to the notion of an upper bound of speed. This upper bound of speed should appear in formulas for p and E because as $v \rightarrow c$ one should have a divergence suggesting that c cannot be attained by a particle with rest mass. The question then becomes: How does formulate this?

Frames Moving with Relative Speeds

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle at rest with m_0 is very different from one moving with v because one must apply a force to the rest particle. One would not consider equivalence of the two. Now, one can view a particle at rest from a frame moving with $-v$. A person in the moving frame thinks he/she is at rest and that the particle moves with v . This means that to the person in the moving frame, the particle has been accelerated and must have at least Newtonian $p = m_0 v$ and $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$. This person may consider a particle at rest with m_0 and $p = 0$ transforming to $m(v)$ and $p = m(v) v$ because p is still considered a flux. This leads to a transformation matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v/c) & v/c \\ v/c & g(v/c) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

It is Newtonian mechanics, we argue that force $g(v/c)$ to be a function other than 1 because m_0 must transform to an expression containing $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ in $v \ll c$ limit. Thus, Newtonian

mechanics guarantees a $g(v/c)$ function. Interestingly, we introduce ((2)) to deal with $m_0, p=0$ becoming $m(v), p$ instead of $x=0, t$ transforming to x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$, which we used as the starting point in a number of previous notes.

Even with ((2)), one still has no idea what $g(v/c)$ is except that it should diverge for $v=c$. One might suspect that it is a function of v/c so that v/c arises as the first order in an expansion for $v \ll c$. Nevertheless, one needs an explicit form for $g(v/c)$.

We suggest that this follows from an unusual argument. In Newtonian mechanics, $m_0, p=0$ and $m(v), p$ are not linked because a rest particle was accelerated and so is completely different now. In the frame scenario. Person A sees a rest mass m_0 and a moving frame ($-v$), while person B thinks he/she is at rest and the rest particle is moving. The two frames are complementary and there should be a relation between $m_0, p=0$ in one frame and $m(v), p$ in the other. This relation is most likely linked with a modulus associated with the Lorentz matrix, but one cannot use the usually Euclidean metric, thus one may propose:

$$E^2 - p^2 c^2 = E'^2 - p'^2 c^2 \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{This leads to } g(v/c) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

c is an upper bound speed associated with a rest mass particle. If one uses:

$$E^2 - p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((5))$$

then for $m_0=0, E=pc$ which is a wave-equation with constant * frequency= E and constant/ p = wavelength. If there is no medium, one might expect a self-wave. A photon is a possible object which satisfies these criteria, but it seems that any particle moving with speed c is equally good. For example, gluons move at c and it was believed that neutrinos did (before they were believed to have a rest mass). There are even papers in the literature suggesting that a photon has a tiny rest mass. Thus, c is simply an upper bound speed which should be very close or identical to the speed of a photon. Thus, in the approach above one does not necessarily have to connect special relativity for a particle with rest mass to electromagnetic theory, (although this theory is directly linked to special relativity).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one might argue for an upper bound speed in Newtonian mechanics. It is already known that rest mass m_0 represents impedance to force and that p is linked with impulse. P is the flux of m_0 , i.e. $KE = .5 m_0 v^2$ is $.5 p v$, i.e. linked with momentum flux and should also represent impedance. The point we make is that as one adds energy to a particle, its impedance to force may increase, making it harder to accelerate the particle and ultimately leading to an upper bound speed. This suggests that more and more energy must be added to the particle as its speed increases close to the upper bound speed c . This, in turn, suggests a divergence expression for energy and momentum when $v=c$.

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle at rest and one moving at v are considered completely different because a force has been applied to the particle at rest. If one considers a particle at

rest and views it from a frame moving with $-v$, people in this frame see a particle moving with v . Thus, they think it has been accelerated and should have Newtonian $p=mv$ and $KE=.5mv^2$. If one tries to link $(p=0, m_0)$ with $(p, m(v))$ using a matrix, then, because p is flux:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v/c) & vg(v/c) \\ vg(v/c) & g(v/c) \end{vmatrix}$$

and $g(v/c)$ cannot be 1. Furthermore, $g(v/c)$ should diverge for $v=c$ and is probably a function of v/c in order to produce $.5mv^2$ to first order. This still does not yield the form of $g(v/c)$. One requires the notion that a function of $m_0, p=0$ in one frame must be equivalent to the same function of $p, m(v)$ in the other frame, because the two frames are complementary, i.e. each frame thinks it is the rest frame and the other is moving. (Thus, the moving frame does not think that just the rest m_0 particle is moving, but the entire rest frame with its co-ordinate axes as well.) Thus, the matrix above may be applied to non-rest mass situations as long as one frame is considered at rest and the other moving, i.e. the matrix may be applied to a photon. Then, one is able to obtain: $g(v/c) = 1 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.